

COMPARATIVE EFFECT OF GUIDED-DISCOVERY AND EXPOSITORY METHOD ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN BIOLOGY IN ILORIN METROPOLIS KWARA STATE.

By

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Abstract

This paper investigated the effects of Guided-discovery and expository method on students' performance in Biology and their effects on gender. The study adopted a protest-prost-test, non randomized experimental group design. Two hundred and forty [240] SS11 Biology students were randomly selected from two co-educational government owned secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis. The test items used in the study was limited to one content area of the Biology curriculum which is circulatory system. The choice of the topic was based on the fact that it has been identified as one of the difficult concepts in the senior secondary school Biology curriculum. A researcher - designed instrument tag Biology Performance Test (BPT) comprising 50 multiple items was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument with Co-efficient of 0.75 was achieved. Three Research questions were raised while three hypotheses were to formulate guide the study. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze the data. The result was verified at 0.05 level of significant difference on the performance of students exposed to two instructional methods. It showed that the Guided-discovery instructional method was superior to Expository method of teaching.

Keywords: *Effects, Guided-discovery, Expository method, Performance, Biology.*

INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The importance of Science and Technology in any nation cannot be over-emphasized. The level of technological development of a society is a measure of the level of scientific literacy obtained in that society. However, Abimbola and Omosewo (2006) define science as a body of knowledge, a way of investigating or method and a way of thinking in the pursuit of understanding of nature. Science is an enterprise that builds and organizes knowledge in the form of testable explanations and predications and about the world.

Abdullahi (1991) state that the basic science subjects comprise biology, chemistry, and physics. In view of this, Ivowi (2000) observe that government has placed priority on science and technology in the past three decades by making it compulsory for all students of post-primary institutions to offer at least one science subject at the secondary school level. It is compulsory at the primary and secondary schools but is a part of general studies for students at the tertiary level.

However, in an attempt to popularize science subjects in Nigerian secondary schools as an important tool for industrial growth and development, Medicine, Engineering, Agriculture and Home economics led to the establishment of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN), on November 30th 1957. The aims of STAN summarized by Fadiaro and Aborishade (1998) include the following:-

- i. Bringing together for mutual help, consultation and advice all those concerned with the teaching of the various branches of science and mathematics at all levels of Nigeria educational system.
- ii. Publishing an official journal and news bulleting to allow for the dissemination of information of recent findings and development of practitioners.

(Iii) Advising Government on the national policy on science education and teaching in Nigeria.

Biology is one of the major science subjects taught in the secondary school curriculum to educate individuals irrespective of the future ambition. According to Sarojini (2000), biology is defined as the study of living things interacting with non living components thus, is the study of life. Biology prepares the individual for choice of careers such as medicine, dentist, agriculture nursing, pharmacy and so on. In spite of the crucial role of biology in human endeavour, students' performance is still very low. Abimbola (1989) observe that inadequate laboratory equipment, lack of adequate teaching methods as well as non-availability of facilities and instructional materials hinder the learner of biology in our secondary schools.

Two instructional methods identified for teaching biology include Guided-Discovery (GD) and Expository (Expo). However, Abdullahi (1982) asserts that expository method of teaching is considered to be teacher centered with an emphasis on content delivery. It is more or less a lecture method. He further observed that expository method does not encourage students to discover the relationship among the variables in a particular science and mathematics structure. Expository method is however capable of equipping students with a means of gaining knowledge on their own through active participation. It encourages learners to explore the content through the use of concrete experience. It is actively engaging learners in first hand, real world learning.

The Guided-Discovery method, is an approach to inquiry, it actively engages learners in first-hand, real world learning. It encourages learners to explore the content through the use of concrete experience. However, the teacher designs experiment for the students to carry out the experiment and the data collected are used to illustrate the concept being taught. Other methods used in teaching and learning of biology include lecture method that

is (talk and chalk), project method among others do expose the students to practical aspect of the course. Pwol (1998) asserts that verbal instructional or lecture method alone is not adequate to ensure the demands of the modern science circular. A major reform in the teaching and learning of science is a shift in emphasis from the traditional, dogmatic textbook and teacher centered approach. Gohan (2000) observes that the chance to be active rather than being passive learners.

Statement of the Problem

Biology is one of the basic science subjects that should be taught with real diverse instructions and learning including real objects and this is well taught with the laboratory set up. Students/learners tend to learn faster and find learning more interesting when they are taught with real instructional materials under the guidance of a teacher as thus emphasizes participatory approach to learning. The most popular method used by the teachers in Nigeria schools is the expository method which has not been yielding good results. It is based on this background that the study is therefore out to investigate the effects of using guided discovery method on students' academic performance in biology.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

- 1 Is there any difference in the performance of biology students taught with Guided-Discovery method and those taught with expository method?
- 2 Is there any difference between the performance of male and female students exposed to Guided discovery and Expository method?

Research Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental design. In this method of research design, the researcher studied the effect of the treatment on intact groups rather than being able to randomly assign participants to the experimental or control groups. The study accepted a pre-test, post-test non-randomize experimental group design.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample of the study would be selected among the SS11 senior secondary school biology students in Ilorin metropolis. The sample selected for the study comprised 240 SS11 students (120 males and 120 females) drawn from Government owned co-educational secondary schools within the town.

Stratified random sampling technique was employed to select the two schools for the experimental and control groups. The instrument comprising 50 multiple items tagged Biology Performance Test (BPT) on circulatory system was a researcher designed questionnaire. It was given to two experienced biology teachers in senior secondary schools and two lecturers' in science education department at the Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. The reliability of the test was determined with the use of test-retest method and this yielded 0.75 which shows high reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to the same after a period of four weeks but re-arranged to give the students impression that the items are different from the pretest.

The data obtained from the study was subjected to analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The statistical analysis is appropriate for testing hypotheses about the effect of more than two independent variables.

H03: There is no significant interaction between the methods used and gender. The results reveal $(1.167) = 0.02$ is less than $F\text{-crit. } 3.07$ and so result

Results

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviation of Post-Test Performance by Instructional Method.

Instructional Method	N	X	SD
GD	120	23.75	6.04
EXPO	120	19.25	7.19

Table 1 reveals that the mean score of the experimental group, (23.75) was superior to the control group of 19.25.

Table 2: Means and SD of post-test by Gender, Method

	Gender	N	X	SD
GD	Female	60	24.70	7.02
	Male	60	25.07	6.89
Expo	Female	60	22.19	8.42
	Male	60	22.10	8.16

Table 2 shows that the mean score of the male students in the experimental (25.07) was higher than that of their female counter-parts (24.07).

Table 3: Summary of a 2 x 2 ANCOVA on instructional Method by Gender.

Source	DF	SS	MF	F	P<0.05
Main effect of instructional method	1	412.68	412.68	11.61	
Gender	1	0.45	0.45	0.02	
Instructional method X Gender	1	347.23	347.27	12.44	NS
Residual	167	49566.7	40.28		
Total	169	5585.74			

$P < 0.05$ f crit. 3.07

Hypotheses

HO1: There is no significant difference in the performance of students exposed to guided discovery and those exposed to expository instructional Method.

The result reveals a significant effect of the instructional method that is treatment $F[1.167]12.18$ is greater than the F crit 4.03 at 7% level of significant difference is hereby rejected.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students exposed to 'Guided' and 'Expository' methods of teaching. The table reveals, F -crit $[1.167] = 0.03$ is less than f -crit, 3.07 at $p \geq 0.05$. This shows that there is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students exposed to the two instructional methods. Thus, HO2 is accepted.

HO3: There is no significant interaction between the methods used and gender. The results reveal $(1.167) = 0.02$ is less than F -crit. 3.07 and so result

is hereby significant interaction between the methods and gender is hereby rejected and the hypotheses is accepted.

Discussion

The results shows that in biology, SS1 students exposed to Guided-Discovery instructional method performed significantly better than those exposed to expository in the Biology Performance test (BPT). From the results, it shown that GD is a good and reliable instructional method which facilitates teaching and learning of biology concepts. This result is contrachers (Ogunleye, 1999) who state that no one method could be considered superior than the other in the various research worked carried out over the years. In line with result obtained, Joju (1981) and Eshiet (1986) reveals that concepts learnt through Guided-Discovery method is better retained in students' memory than those just described through expository method.

The results show further that gender does not have any significant effect on students' performance when exposed to two methods. The findings also show a significant interaction exists between gender and teaching method adopted.

Implications

It has been found out that Guided discovery is superior to Expository approach because in a guided discovery, the teacher designs experiments for students to perform. The data collected were used to illustrate the concept being taught. However, teaches should try to expose their students to practical work and integrate this with some theory while adopting the guided discovery method.

Conclusion

Guided-discovery method is a method that cannot be discarded in teaching in teaching learning process. The study has shown that the use of Guided discovery in the delivery of instruction has potentially played a dominant role in education. However, in order to make the method more realistic in the teaching/learning processes, the teachers need to be encourage regularly to execute this method and integrate it unto their teaching.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

- * Biology teachers should employ guided discovery method to make their teaching/learning process more interesting, efficient and motivating.
- * Biology textbook writers should focus more attention on the discovery skill.
- * Biology students should also be focused or see the need to adopt this instructional method in their learning.
- * Curriculum planners should encourage and support the biology teachers in the use of this method both financially and morally.
- * Also, Government should give enough fund for education facilities to combat those serious challenge inhibiting the fast and inevitable use of information and communication technology in our secondary schools.

There is the need for Nigerian government to address seriously the issues of erratic electricity supply while schools wishing to integrate the use of ICT in their teaching-learning process should as a matter of urgency procure a generating set or alternative current, that could supplement Power Holding Company (PHCN) for supply of power.

Key words: Activity-based teaching, students' performance, Biology

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